

Politeness in Asynchronous Computer Mediated Discourse in Nairaland

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Abstract

Innovations in the Internet that changed from static to user-generated content web pages made social network sites popular. This change in turn attracted the attention of scholars from different fields of human endeavour. This study aimed to make a contribution from linguistics and language study by examining politeness in interactions on a Nigerian social network site, Nairaland. The various threads of interactions posted on the site from 1 - 4 May, 2012, made up the data for the study. The threads were sorted by topic and subjected to pragmatic analysis. Basing its analysis on the theory of politeness and relational work, the study examined how interactants on Nairaland carry out face work and discovered that three types of relational work: politic verbal behaviour, polite verbal behaviour and impolite verbal behaviour were prominent in the interactions of Nigerians who converge on this site. The study found that interactions on Nairaland are characterized by flaming, agonism and mostly impoliteness. These features were traced to the anonymity and the asynchronous nature of Nairaland forum. The study would be of immense benefits to academics in the field of pragmatics, in particular and language study in general.

Keywords: Nairaland, politeness, relational work, verbal behaviour

Résumé

Les innovations sur l'internet qui sont passées de pages Web statiques à des pages Web de contenu générées par les utilisateurs, ont rendu populaires les sites de réseaux sociaux. De sa part, ce changement a attiré l'attention des chercheurs de différents domaines de l'activité humaine. Cette étude vise à apporter la contribution de la linguistique et l'étude des langues qui évaluent la politesse dans les interactions sur un site de réseau social nigérian, Nairaland. Les différents contenus d'interactions postés sur le site du 1er au 4 mai 2012 ont constitué les données de la présente étude. Les contenus ont été repartis par sujet et soumis à une analyse pragmatique. Basant son analyse sur la théorie de la politesse et du travail relationnel, l'étude a examiné comment les intervenants sur Nairaland effectuent des travaux de manière face-à-face et a découvert que trois types de travail relationnel tel: le comportement verbal politique, le comportement verbal poli et le comportement verbal impoli caractérisent les Nigériens qui se croisent sur ce site web. L'étude a montré que les interactions sur Nairaland sont caractérisées par l'émotion, l'agonie et surtout l'impolitesse. Ces caractéristiques sont attribuées à l'anonymat et à la nature asynchrone du forum Nairaland. L'étude présenterait d'immenses avantages pour les universitaires dans le domaine de la pragmatique et en particulier pour l'étude des langues en général.

Mots-clés: Nairaland, politesse, travail relationnel, comportement verbal

Introduction

Politeness in human interaction has been of interest among social and linguistic scholars for so many years now. This interest has led to many research attempts, which have shown distinction between polite behaviour and what is not. Most of these attempts are based on Brown & Levinson's (1987) framework. Though this research direction is prominent, it has been challenged because of its not being able to account for the whole array of realizations of politeness phenomena in human society (Odebunmi, 2009). The basic concepts favoured by Brown & Levinson's (1987) framework: the norms of appropriateness, the concepts of face and other sociopragmatic issues are today accepted to be rather culture-specific. Given these discrepancies in the realizations of these phenomena in different contexts, the question that begs for an answer is if politeness and self-presentation are specific to genre or medium of communication.

Using Anderson's (1983) concept of imagined communities, Rheingold (1993:5), defines virtual online communities (VOC henceforth) as "social aggregations that emerge from the Net when enough people carry on those public discussions long enough, with sufficient human feeling, to form webs of personal relationships in cyberspace." This takes VOCs as imagined communities or social aggregations that exist long enough for individuals to form personal relationships. Thus, this study defines VOCs as 'global villages' – collectivities of people bounded by technology and common interests, unconstrained by geographic distance, based on common interest rather than common location (Benwell&Stokoe, 2006). Due to the virtuality of these online communities, there is a simulation of human interaction where one can see constructs of people, personalities, emotion, language, and relationships (Budiman, 2008). Research has proven that a virtual environment is not meant to provide a replacement of reality, but offers an extension of self-identity. This is because expression of self-identity in the real world may be restricted by social norms and culture, but a virtual environment provides a free and open platform for self-expression.

Studies in Social Sciences have examined how VOCs influence self-presentation and expression (e.g. Dominick, 1999; Papacharissi, 2002b, 2007;Walker, 2000), and the structural and design elements of online social networks employed to foster connection-sharing, social capital generation and effective communication. In linguistics, studies on VOCs are just emerging. This is because the history of VOCs is also very young. In Nigeria, the picture is the same as people are just getting interested in CMC-CMD. The present study aims to contribute to the literature by examining politeness strategies in interactions on a VOC in Nigeria known as Nairaland.net. The motivation for the study arises from three factors. First, the lean linguistic literature on the study of VOCs in Nigeria; the fact that these new media are sites for different and new forms of interactional behaviours and strategies and so make them rich data sources for linguistic research; and the opportunity to apply Politeness theory, which is an emerging area of pragmatic research to the study of CMC.

Politeness and Relational Work

Several models of politeness theories have been espoused in linguistics. These include those of Lakoff, Brown & Levinson, Leech, Ide, Blum Kulka, Gu, Fraser and Nolan, Arndt and Janney, and Watts (Eden 2001). Common to all these models are their concentration on the distinction between polite and impolite behaviour and only a few have given account of what has been called politic or acceptable acts by most post-modern theorists of politeness. However, Watts (2003) is different in this regard. Therefore, we shall review his theory of relational work (Watts, 2003; Locher & Watts, 2005) as it shall form our theoretical basis and expand this theory with insights from Brown and Levinson's FTA framework for a proper characterisation of politeness.

The theory of relational work was propounded by Watts (1989, 1992, 2003). However, other influential scholars like Kasper (1990), Locher (2004) and Locher & Watts (2005) have made contributions to the model. In their approach, Locher & Watts (2005) criticise Brown & Levinson's (1987 [1978]) framework that it does not deal with politeness but with mitigation of FTAs in general. As a result of this, much of what has been defined as polite in literature is, according to them, merely appropriate behaviour. Locher & Watts (2005) therefore argue for a discursive approach to politeness which reduces politeness to a much smaller part of relational work, which has to be considered with respect to other realizations of interpersonal meaning. According to them, relational work refers to "work" individuals invest in negotiating relationships with others. (Locher & Watts, 2005, p.10). Odeunmi (2009), explaining this, claims it implies that the interactants are accustomed to a particular relational mode, and that many utterances that pass between them are expected, given the context of interaction.

According to Okamoto (1999, p. 51):

Expressions of politeness are relative to specific social contexts as well as to the speakers' ideas about politeness. An adequate account of linguistic politeness thus requires a close examination of the relationship among linguistic expressions in discourse, speakers' ideas about politeness, and social context.

Okamoto's words serve to prove that the theory of relational work has been hinged on context, and not on the notion that politeness is inherent in the expression, as held by theorists of face work. The relational work theory is seen to be broader than facework, and is capable of handling directness, impoliteness, rudeness/aggressiveness and polite interaction, including verbal behaviours that are either appropriate or inappropriate.

Locher & Watts maintain that prior dichotomies of polite and impolite behaviour found in the theory of face work (Brown & Levinson, 1987 [1978]; Culpeper, 1996, 2005; Culpeper, et al., 2003; Escandell-Vidal, 1996; Fraser, 1990; Lakoff, 1973; Leech, 1983; Meier, 1995b; Mills, 2003, 2005) should be replaced with a continuum in which politeness only represents a small part of relational work. In addition, they are in favour of a further distinction within appropriate behaviour (Locher, 2004; Locher & Watts, 2005; Watts, 1989, 1992, 2003), namely non-polite yet appropriate/politic behaviour, on the one hand, and appropriate/politic but similarly polite behaviour, on the other. The term politic has thereby been introduced by Watts (1989) who defines it as "that behaviour, linguistic and non-linguistic, which the

participants construct as being appropriate to the ongoing social interaction” (Watts, 2003, p. 257). Polite behaviour hence describes behaviour which is seen as appropriate in lay people’s perceptions, because it is the kind of behaviour they would expect to happen in this situation. Polite behaviour, in contrast to that, goes beyond what is expected and is hence seen in this approach as *surplus* (Kasper, 1990; Locher, 2004; Watts, 1989, 1992). With these definitions, Kasper (1990), Watts (1989, 1992), and Locher (2004) clearly differ from Fraser’s (1975, 1990) view in that politeness is not only regarded as unmarked appropriate behaviour, but as a marked behaviour, which stands above the norm and is thus recognised in interactions, as it goes beyond interactants’ expectations.

Central to Locher& Watts’ (2005) concept of relational work is Goffman’s (1967) notion of face. Locher& Watts agrees with Goffman (1967) that face is not inherent in each individual but constructed in every individual discourse. Face is thus socially attributed anew in each specific interaction, which implies that every individual can have a large number of faces. Locher& Watts (2005) hence equate them with “masks, on loan to us for the duration of different kinds of performance” (Locher& Watts, 2005, p. 12), which an individual may even want to change within the course of an interaction, as we are not “tied to just one single role” (Locher, 2006b). With this discursive concept of face, relational work comprises a more comprehensive notion of face. Also crucial to Locher& Watts’ (2005) discursive approach of politeness is the fact that it is based on the notion of first order politeness (politeness1), i.e. the lay concept of politeness, rather than second order politeness (politeness2) which makes use of the terms “polite” and “politeness” as theoretical constructs (Watts, et al., 1992). As they claim that no linguistic expression is inherently polite and, at the same time, individuals’ realisations and understanding of utterances may vary due to their different habits. Locher& Watts see no point in maintaining a universal theoretical concept of politeness (Locher, 2006a, 2006b; Locher& Watts, 2005). Instead of imposing second order principles on linguistic data, whose results often do not coincide with individual’s perception of politeness, what they want is “to recognize that terms such as ‘impolite’, ‘polite’ or ‘appropriate’ are inherently evaluative and normative” (Locher, 2006b, p. 252).

The notion of face that relational work gives account of is the same with what is characterised by Brown and Levinson’s face-work theory. Face has been characterised as ‘the public self-image of a person’ and the “emotional and social feeling of self which an individual has and expects others to recognize” (Yule 1996:60, Odebunmi 2003, Adebite and Odebunmi 2004). Therefore, there are positive face and negative face. Adebija (1989) describes the positive face as that which satisfies a speaker’s need for approval and belonging while negative face serves to minimize the imposition of face-threatening act.

Central to Brown and Levinson’s (1987) work are what they call the face-saving and face-threatening acts. A person’s face is saved “when the person’s face wants are met,” while the person’s face is threatened when a person’s face wants are not met. Moreover, face threatening acts can be seen as illocutionary acts that can damage or threaten an individual’s positive or negative face (Odebunmi 2002, 2009). Another characterization of Brown and

Levinson (1987) in the literature is the off-record strategy. This enables a speaker to avoid responsibility for performing an FTA either by engaging conversational implicatures or by being intentionally vague or ambiguous (Mullany 2002). Conversely, if speaker chooses an on record strategy, he/she can either perform FTA without redressive action, known as “going baldly on record,” or he can perform the FTA with redressive action (Odebunmi 2002, Mullany 2002, p.3).

Politeness and Computer-Mediated Communication (CMC)

Tannen (1999) holds that the anonymity created by CMC is one of the causes of agonism in contemporary American culture. Many social and communication theorists have speculated on the influence of the medium on verbal behaviour in CMC. For instance, social presence theory (Short, et al., 1976) claims that the social impact of a communication medium depends on the social presence it offers communicators. Text-based forms of interaction are viewed as less social and thus less encouraging of social influence. This theory assumes that the de-individuation of the conversational partner that happens in the medium of CMC may lead to anti-social behaviour. This kind of premise permeates studies that have been carried out so far on social behaviour online. For instance, Herring (1996) studied gender differences in CMC in the US, and found that females are more geared towards maintaining positive politeness, whereas males are more attuned to the adversarial or anarchistic nature of the medium. Both groups, however, appear to be roughly equal in terms of maintaining negative politeness. Other works have also studied interactional behaviour online and though these are not so many, have come up with the findings that the medium of the Internet somewhat aids anti-social behaviour and aggression (Herring & Nix, 1997, p. 1; Merchant, 2001, p. 295; Cho et al., 2005). For instance, Hardaker (2010) holds that while computer-mediated communication (CMC) can benefit users by providing quick and easy communication between those separated by time and space, it can also provide varying degrees of anonymity that may encourage a sense of impunity and freedom from being held accountable for inappropriate online behaviour. As such, CMC is a fertile ground for studying impoliteness. She proves this claim by her investigation of trolling in some online discussions.

Politeness, CMC and Nigeria Socio-cultural Context

It has been pointed out in many studies, Adegbite and Odebunmi (2010), Odebunmi (2005 & 2013), Obins (2015), Olaniyi (2017) that Nigerians bring over politeness strategies in their different ethno-cultural group into interaction in English. For instance, Odebunmi (2005 & 2013) claims that Yoruba people are generally deferent and polite and that they use different discursive means to show this. This is confirmed by Obins (2015) who claims that Nigerians like to show politeness in communication and show through many linguistic means that agree with most of the postulates in the literature on politeness about the nature and types of politeness. Despite these assertions, the context of CMC tends to have its effects on this socio-cultural norm. While many pragmatic strategies conspicuously show that many of the interactants are Nigerians, the findings of scholars like Tannen (1999), (Herring & Nix, 1997, p. 1; Merchant, 2001, p. 295; Cho et al., 2005) are confirmed in this study that the anonymous nature of the medium of CMC is one important reason for

rudeness and impolite behaviour in the discourse that emanates from the genre. Therefore, despite the other unique characteristics Nigerians bring to bear on their interactions, the anonymity of CMC influences their performance of politeness and identity construction in this medium.

Methodology

Data

The analytical method favoured in this study is that of content analysis and the politeness theory of Watts & Locher (2005). This theoretical model will be applied to data sourced from the discussion forum of Nairaland.net. Fifty topics of discussions were selected based on subject matter. These threads were posted in the month of May, 2012 and they are on issues ranging from socio-political occurrences to sports and entertainment.

Nairaland is an online community created by Nigerian webmaster SeunOsewa in March 2005. It is targeted at Nigerians and is the biggest community on the Internet where Nigerians congregate. Members consist of Nigerians at home and in the Diaspora. Nairaland is a forum. A forum is simply a website made up of threads where issues can be discussed. Nairaland has threads and discussions on matters happening in Nigerian and matters affecting Nigerians. Nairaland is divided into many categories where people can discuss issues bordering on family and marriage, romance and sexuality, politics, business, career, education, health, religion, travel, fashion, books, music/radio, TV/movies, jokes etc. poems, sports, games, computers, phones, and of course, the Internet. There are sections for Developers, Webmasters, Job seekers, and a bulletin board for Adverts. The content of the site consists mostly of posts and threads started by its users and it often takes the form of debates and discussions.

The nature of Nairaland tends towards argumentation as members are expected to state their opinions on specific subjects that have been raised in the threads created by some of them. In stating their opinions, members tend to have opinion clash, which results into flaming, agonism and very rude behaviour in form of insults and name calling. This mostly occurs under threads that have to do with socio-political issues and sports as we will see in the analysis. Insults and name calling at times may not be directed to members but towards the actors in the subjects being discussed which are outside the context of Nairaland, but in the context of Nigeria as a country.

Politeness in Nairaland

As a discussion forum, the most prominent feature found in Nairaland forum is that of argumentation. This makes participants prone to sentimentality and negative behaviour. But at times, depending on the topic, the mood of discussion is light and funny so participants just express their feelings or views about a particular topic in a humorous way.

Three aspects of relational work are found in the data; namely, politic verbal behaviour, polite verbal behaviour and impolite verbal behaviour. From our findings in the data, we discovered that context is common to the interactants. This includes: shared

knowledge of subjects, shared knowledge of sociocultural and socio-political issues and shared knowledge of nationality. With this contextual background, participants produce politic verbal behaviour, polite verbal behaviour, and impolite verbal behaviour, which are respectively characterized by criticisms, assertions, humour, sympathy and condemnations, accusations, flaming and agonism. The analysis that follows illustrates these features clearly and discusses their pragmatic implications.

Politic Verbal Behaviour

This pragmatic behaviour is performed when topics like Nigeria's sociopolitical issues and political leaders are not discussed. In this context, the mood is light and comments that are criticisms, assertions, even name calling tend to be taken as normal and appropriate to the situation. The responses to these threads of discussion are not taken as aggressive or rude. Few examples of these are found under threads on sports and romance.

Example 1:

A: (The thread): How Many Of You Got/wrote This Kind Of Letter?

B: 1993? Most people on Nairaland were not born then. . .

E: Do I seriously mean most people on nairaland are less dan 20yrs old, no wonder one get some childish responses from some people

F: Don't be suprised, the guy who wrote that was probably born around then. 🇳🇮

J: And you believed that? you'd also believe chamakh is better than messi

The participant who started this thread started it on a note of humour, but the assertion that follows takes it to a level that could have caused a verbal war that could result to insulting and name calling, but this kind of assertion is regarded by most participants as part of the joke on which note the thread started. Even when some participants responded on a serious note of criticism of participant's age and contributions, they were ignored or their comments were taken as part of the joke. For instance, participant F actually threatened the negative face of participant A who started the thread. In another situation, this would have been taken as impolite and would have caused participant A or any other participant to reproach participant F by name calling and insults, but this does not happen because what s/he has done is taken as appropriate to the situation, that is, insulting at times is part of jokes.

At times the issue raised may be on a serious note to which participants may respond to with criticisms and assertions that are coined in funny expressions. Example two below illustrates this.

Example 2:

A (The thread): T. B. Joshua Did Not Prophecy About Chelsea In Champions League!!!

TB JOSHUA DID NOT PROPHECY ABOUT CHELSEA IN THE UEFA CHAMPIONS LEAGUE!!! There have been several rumours circulating that Prophet T.B. Joshua prophesied the outcome of the UEFA Champions League Final. This message is to set the record straight: Prophet TB Joshua did not prophecy concerning the upcoming UEFA Champions League Final. Prophet TB Joshua did not prophecy concerning which team would win the UEFA Champions League Final. Prophet TB Joshua did not prophecy concerning who should play or who should not play in the Champions League Final match.

We must stop lying against the man of God, Prophet T.B. Joshua. This is a tactic of the enemy – to say what he has not said and say he is the one that said it. Every prophetic message given by Prophet T.B. Joshua is broadcast LIVE on Emmanuel TV and online. If you don't see it on Emmanuel TV, it didn't happen. "Touch not My anointed and do My prophets no harm." (Psalm 105:15)

F: what a pity? Chelsea fans were already rejoicing. Don't worry maybe another prophecy would come

G: Hehehe 🤔. After seeing Chelsea thoroughly and comprehensively thrashed and left for dust by Newcastle, it's panic stations for the T.B Joshua camp.

Nice attempt at damage limitation and outright denial though 😊.

J: Yes, but watch out how dogs will come denying that there was a denial of the prediction if Chelsea does win. One thing always come to respect this SCOAN people for: they do cover all their Bases, head or tail, their prophet is made to be the winner

K: So TBJ is your prophet and anointed? SMH.

Whoever follows Him and heeds His commandments is actually the anointed. Right?

L: The Church is playing Safe

M: Who is deceiving who?

From these threads of discussion, it shows that the first participant who started the thread is a member of T.B. Joshua's church in the way he warns the people discussing his prophet sternly by using quotation from the Bible. However, most of the participants that responded to the thread did so with criticisms and assertions that could have started a flame war in some other contexts. As it is expected when it comes to the issue of religion and men claiming to know the mind of God, the criticisms were not taken as offence. So in this situation, they pass for polite verbal behaviour.

Polite Verbal Behaviour

Participants in the interactions exhibit polite verbal behaviour when they see the need to create an environment of peace maybe after a flame war has preceded their responses or when the topic being discussed is not of a sensitive and serious nature. But this comes, most often, in form of humour and jokes in the interactions or as normal discussion that people enjoy. Example three below serves to illustrate this.

Example 3:

A (the thread): Yakubu Makes List of Best Signings Of The 2011/2012 EPL Season

B: Yakubu is one of best striker in EPL has scoring ability.

C: he is actually 4th on the scoring log.

D: The Demba twins are definitely the best deals, low cost – high quality signings

Yakubu try this season sha. 🤔

E: Na Cisse u dey call Demba Ba twin brother?

F: figure of speech mate 😊

From the interactions above, it shows that the interactants are really enjoying the discussion as the subject of discussion is something they enjoy and makes them relax. In this context, rudeness, insults and name calling most often do not occur. There is a note of agreement and happiness in the discussion. This can be seen in one of the emoticons in the threads. Aside this, people also express polite verbal behaviour in form of jokes and humour. The example below shows this.

Example 4:

A (thread): How Many Of You Got/wrote This Kind Of Letter?

C: i tell u my guy, good old days

H: I remember writing something like this too!

I: yes yesi remember DOXOLOGY and DITOMATIC and MY GOLDEN PEN etc were Commomgrammars back in the days

M: where did this come from? I was in pry 6 that yr. i know nothing like love letters. how timeflies!

S: hmm.....the good old days, when you end letters with something like ‘I drop my pen in the Basket of love’ it was realy fun

T: U wouldn’t bliv how glad I am I had my fair share of writing those letters. Had a bad Experience wen my teen boo forgot the letter in her school bag and the mum found it. So glad I didn’t put my name. So the mum was busy lukin 4 who ditto is in d neighbourhood! good olldays! Heard she married with kids now though! Lol!

U: lol@my heart beat gbangbam. funny love-drunk dude

W: 🤪🤪🤪🤪🤪🤪🤪🤪

Olden days funnyooo

X: Just one page ? 🤪🤪🤪mine was about 4 pages. . . 🤪

Z: I don’t like to write letter because the girl may expose the letter to her friends. they will start Call u okoiyawoeleponbulu. Ha hahaha.

In the above interaction, politeness is achieved by humour. Most of the participants are in agreement and in a funny mood. Just as the poster of the thread had wanted to accomplish. This shows that humour and jokes are some of the pragmatic strategies used to express polite verbal behaviour on Nairaland. It also shows the kind of subject under discussion: romance, which most often is personal so people tend to express how they feel without having to threaten anyone.

Another way in which polite verbal behaviour is expressed in the data is through sympathy. Example 5 gives an illustration of this.

Example 5:

A (thread): RashidiYekini– Nigerian Soccer Legend Is Reported Dead In City of Ibadan

D: Saw it too. RIP

E: if na true, may his soul rest in peace.

F: Please can someone confirm this?

G: Its confirmed... RIP

K: may jentle soul rest in perfect peace...he was the best we ever had!

In this thread, polite verbal behaviour is achieved through the expression of sympathy for Rashidi Yekini who was once a soccer star in Nigeria. This kind of thread on Nairaland usually brings Nairalanders together as one as they express a general view about that particular thing, in this case the loss of a national hero. In addition to sympathy, polite behaviour is also expressed in the data through gratitude. This usually occurs in a thread that is expository in nature, that is, a thread that teaches about the usefulness of something or that enlightens participants about any particular thing. The example below shows this.

Example 6:

A (thread): The Need To Have A Tyre Pressure Gauge

C: Thanks for this revelation. Will go get my tire gauge ASAP

D: nice idea! Nid 2 get mined sooner!! A friend told me its 5k

E: Will definitely get one ASAP. This is very good Ikenna

H: This is a very important topic and I must say thank you bros for this topic. Pls can anyone

Direct me to where I can get one in Lagos around Lekki phase 1?

Impolite Verbal Behaviour

Impolite verbal behaviour is the most predominant Politeness strategy found in the data. This occurs as condemnation or accusation, flaming and agonism. These kinds of verbal behaviour is put up when participants feel that the issues raised do not agree with their view points or sound 'stupid' to them. On these occasions, participants display aggressive poses, rudeness to discredit the other party. They result to name calling and insults to confront the party with its views, defend their points of view or protect their interests. To achieve this, unmitigated threats, tallying with a large part of face work's FTA without redress is invoked. This FTA does not include all direct expressions as we have in the face work literature, but only those that practically make the other participant feel uncomfortable. The instances found in the data manifest in the form of insults, name calling, bullying, cursing and outright rudeness. Let see the example below.

Example 7:

A (thread): Olaitan Oyerinde, Gov. Oshiomole's Private Secretary Murdered

C: So PDP In Edo is tryin to fix dis election by every means possible? Shame!

D: When people head go take correct for this place. His assistant was murdered by whom?

Why is it Ok to simply suggest that PDP did it? Why not INVESTIGATE and FOUND OUT WHO THE MURDER really is for pete's sake?

G: The man is governor for pete's sake. If he wants to stop seeming like a joke, he needs to start doing a better job by keeping his trap shut a bit more and letting the EVIDENCE speak for itself. So far, for the many claims that the opposition is after him, there has been no solid evidence. Makes me doubt his sanity even.

The above example is an illustration of insults. Here, the participants' reactions to the news

thread started by A is that of anger and this led into insulting PDP as the ruling party in Nigeria and believed by many average Nigerians as a bad party, insulting the person who insulted PDP and even Edo State governor who insinuated in his reaction to the murder that the opposition party was after him. Insulting socio-political actors and even co-participants is a common FTA in Nairaland forum, especially on threads that have to do with Nigeria's socio-political issues. This kind of FTA is produced by participants not just against social actors or people mentioned in the discussion alone, but also to co-participants on the forum. This kind of behaviour leads to flaming and what we call agonism (always ready to fight and insult people). The example below is a good instance of how participants on Nairaland start the flaming war.

Example 8:

A (thread): A (thread): Olaitan Oyerinde, Gov. Oshiomole's Private Secretary Murdered

R: I just don't know how people lyk u will just open ur mouth to spit foul and unconfirmed and unverified reports.....how do you mean PDP is a den of killers? so funsho Williams (who is aPDP) WAS ALSO MURDERED BY PDP? isthgat how u draw your senseless conclusion. did u even go to school at all? dont you know as a politician in Nigeria, u are susceptible to attack because there might be cases where they refused to pay homage (either to hoodlums which they hired for election or whatever who den comes and hunt them again). You don't just open ur stinking mouth without making proper research as to possible reason why we had series of killings...did u think Oshiomole is "clean"? or is he a saint?

T: just look at ur post.....sound rather myopic and does not reflect you attended a primary school at all. is the person in question a lady? meaning you did not take time to read and digest the topic before u spew rubbish out of your blank head through ur foul mouth. Can you justify dat the pple or group u named above did the killing? dats why I will continue to say GEJ IS BY FAR BETTER THAN SO MANY PPLE/CRITICS on this platform

X: In the Nigeria politics, nobody is a saint. Those calling GEJ and PAD need to examine their brains if any. Is a Adams a saint or above the law to call for questioning by the security agents? Few days ago, he lost 3 solid human beings and he came out to tell the public that they want to assassinate him. For him to make such statement, he has suspects, he should come out and tell people whom his suspects are. Or has he offended some people he is secretly paying? I don't get it why an innocent blood should flow for a person who doesn't deserve it.

Edo state or its governor doesn't worth any human blood. Enough of all these blood politics.

Z: So you that graduated from Primary School and couldn't pass 'FIRST SCHOOL LEAVING' did not notice the sacarsm in my post!!

I suggest you google 'Figure of speech' and be enlightened. . Oxymoron. . . And that was not an insult either!! 😊

(The whole thread needs to be followed from the beginning to capture the post itself). From the threads above we can see a flame war among participants. In this kind of situation, participants go beyond the extreme to express the fact that their own views or camp has been badly accused or criticised by co-participants. In these threads, it can be seen that these

participants reacted to a thread that has gone before in a very aggressive and rude way. By so, doing they perform FTAs without redressive action.

Another relational strategy used to express impolite verbal behaviour in the data is name calling. To do this, participants use all manner of names and descriptions to express their anger and aggression towards a particular view, person, participant or even social actor. The example below illustrates this.

Example 9:

A (thread): OlaitanOyerinde, Gov. Oshiomole's Private Secretary Murdered

E: Naija politics Game of Death

Unfortunate loss

G: Has any good ever come out of the countless investigations of opposition politicians in Nigeria? Bola ige, funshowilliams, diposhina, etc? We all know pdp is s den of killers.

I: The more scums like that die,the better foe innocent Nigerians. That is if there are innocent

Nigerians left in that dungeon. The country is in a dog eat dog pact. Even kids are up for whatthey can aggressively grab at the expense of others.

(The names or tags used should be underlined for clarity)

From the threads of discussion above, we see the kinds of bad names and descriptions that have been given to Nigerian politics (a game of death). This paints Nigerian politicians in a very bad light and accuses them of being desperate for power that they stoop low to the level of killing others. PDP is called a den of killers, which outright means that every Nigerian politician connected to PDP is a murderer. The person who has been reported dead is given his own name. He is called a 'scum' and the use of the word shows that most Nigerian politicians or those who work for them are 'scums' that are seen as people who need to die for 'good' Nigerians to be happy. Nigeria as a country is even called a dungeon where we may likely not find innocent people. These FTAs are used by these participants to express their hopelessness and distrust in Nigerian leaders, politicians and the country as a whole.

In example ten, the participants in the interactions actually resort to cursing to express their anger and dislike towards a person or a particular point of view.

Example 10:

A (Thread): Canada To Deport A Nigerians' Hater, KemiOmololu-Olunloyo Back To Nigeria

R: GOOD! That filthy old hag sure got what she deserves!

Can you believe the idiot once posted pictures of Archi students doing their school Archi

CAD assignments with their laptops in their hostel room, and she said they were people doing SCAMS? Words can't describe how much I hate this biitchh!

I hope, as she's being deported, her plane is hijacked by 700 Mutallabs, and she's blown to pieces in mid-air.

FUCCKIING ARSE!

Here, this participant resorts to cursing to express the magnitude of his hate towards the person the thread is about. This kind of strategy shows that the person being discussed must be a very terrible person in society that most of the participants do not wish well. While other participants called her different abusive and derogatory tags, this person's curse acts show the height of the kind of aggression towards her.

Conclusion

On the whole, we have demonstrated that much of what transpires between participants in interactions on Nairaland forum is informed by previously or spontaneously conceived opinions which may be presented directly, using politic, polite or impolite expressions. These features are very useful premise for generalizations on the genre, and they also aid a better understanding of the interactions. One major factor that we discovered in our findings is the fact that this forum serves as a place where participants can let out their frustrations against socio-political issues in Nigeria and the meanest of their character traits, which they may not be able to express elsewhere. We can rightly say then that the medium of interaction, which gives the advantage of anonymity aids these impolite verbal behaviours. This study then agrees with scholars who claim that CMC aids such anti-social behaviour like agonism and flaming. The study thus gives very useful information about politeness in CMC, especially in virtual online communities in Nigeria, where extremely little work yet exists. Future research can explore politeness in other types of CMC where there is less anonymity like Facebook using relational work theory.

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